

**REGULATION OF THE PROCESS OF CIVIL SERVICE IN THE PUBLIC
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14645699>**Annotation:**

This article analyzes the issues of legal regulation of the process of passing civil service. The author examines the relations related to civil service from the perspectives of administrative and labor law, highlighting the intersection of these two areas of law. Additionally, the article discusses the differences between the dispositive nature of labor law and the imperative requirements of civil service in the legal regulation process. The necessity of improving legal norms in the field of civil service and the importance of its regulation by administrative law are substantiated.

Keywords:

Civil service, administrative law, labor law, passing civil service, legal regulation, imperative and dispositive methods, civil servants, state-service relations, corruption prevention.

The relations regarding the process of passing civil service require comprehensive scientific analysis. In the theory of administrative law, there is no unified approach to the concepts of "civil service" and "passing civil service." This is due to the theoretical and practical issues related to matters such as appointment to civil service, granting of rank, certification of civil servants, and others, as well as the lack of scientific research in this area.

One of the most pressing issues in the legal regulation of the process of passing civil service is its relationship with either labor law or administrative law. It is important to note that the intersection of administrative and labor law most directly relates to civil service relations.

A number of scholars (S.A. Ivanov, A.M. Kurennoy, S.P. Mavrin, E.B. Khokhlov, L.A. Chikanova) consider the relations between a civil servant and a state authority to be labor law relations. Accordingly, they emphasize that these relations should be regulated by labor law norms, taking into account the specifics defined in the special legal documents on civil service. G.S. Skachkova interprets the contracts made with civil servants as a type of labor contract with administrative-legal characteristics. In general, these contracts have two

features: when entering civil service, they involve labor relations like those of an ordinary citizen, and after joining the service, they transition into administrative-legal relations upon obtaining the authority of a state body.

Labor law representative R.Z. Livshits emphasizes that labor law is a separate field from civil law, but he does not deny that administrative law is one of the closest areas of law to labor law.

Other scholars (Y.A. Starilov, A.A. Grishkovets, A.F. Nozdraev) consider the service contract to have administrative-legal elements. This approach is based on the fact that civil service is an integral system of public law.

B.N. Gabrychidze highlights that the administrative law norms regulating civil service and the labor law norms that define the procedure for acceptance into civil service and passing through it are so closely related that it is sometimes difficult to draw a clear line between them. He emphasizes that this field must be regulated from an administrative-legal perspective.

It should also be added that the interrelation of administrative and labor law is linked to the method that should be used to regulate the work of civil servants. That is, the legal regulation of civil service is based on a combination of imperative and dispositive approaches. Today, labor law is becoming more dispositive in nature. However, civil service is more inclined toward imperativeness than dispositiveness. By establishing clear limitations within civil service, additional social guarantees are provided, which helps prevent conflicts of interest and corruption.

A significant part of the legal support for civil servants consists of the employees of the executive authorities of the state, which is a crucial part of the administrative law system. This creates a need for the sector to be regulated by administrative-legal means.

In our view, relations regarding passing civil service must be regulated by administrative law, which can be justified as follows: First, these relations are directly related to the subjects of administrative law, including executive authorities and officials. Second, these relations are associated with important institutions of administrative law, such as administrative justice and civil service.

The legal relationship between the state and service is the relationship between the state employer and the civil servant. In the process of implementing these state legal relations, a specific state function of state policy is carried out. State-service relations should be distinct from labor relations. Labor legal relations have a private legal nature, where the subjects are equal. The

occurrence of labor relations is sufficient with the conclusion and signing of a single labor contract. The force of the labor contract begins when the employee gains their legal status, and they must adhere to the organization's internal labor regulations and labor regime.

State-service relations are administrative-legal relations, which are not private like labor relations but serve the realization of state and public relations. In such legal relations, the parties are not equal in terms of authority, as the civil servant submits to the state.

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